

Risk Factors for Intra-Uterine Growth Retardation and its Outcomes in a Tertiary Care Hospital

Aditi Saini¹, Abhilasha Thakyal², Harshita Moza³, Anumodan Gupta⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SMGS Hospital, GMC, Jammu

²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SMGS Hospital, GMC, Jammu

³Post-graduate Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SMGS Hospital, GMC, Jammu

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, SMGS Hospital, GMC, Jammu

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Harshita Moza

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Abstract:

Introduction: Reduced fetal growth is seen in about 10% of the pregnancies but only a minority has a pathological background and is known as intrauterine growth restriction or fetal growth restriction (IUGR / FGR). The reported incidence of SGA ranges from 10% to 27% worldwide. Fetal growth is regulated at multiple levels. Increased fetal and neonatal mortality and morbidity as well as adult pathologic conditions are often associated with IUGR. The present study was done to evaluate the risk factors and neonatal outcome of IUGR.

Material and Method: The present prospective study was conducted at the department of obstetrics and gynaecology of SMGS Hospital among 300 pregnant women with IUGR during the study period of one year. Risk factors and neonatal outcome were noted and results were analysed using SPSS 25.0.

Result: The study revealed the maximum number of cases (56.6%) belonged to the age between 20 to 30 years. IUGR was common in Multigravida (75%), rural area (55.6%). IUGR was observed in 49% with normal AFI and severe oligohydramnios <5 cm was observed in 19%. Doppler velocimetry showed abnormal umbilical S/D ratio in 39 (13%). Most of the patients (66%) required a caesarean section. A total of 187 (62.4%) neonates had birth weight ranging between 2.5 to 3.0 kg. (36%) neonates had morbidity and (1.7%) had mortality.

Conclusion: By studying the risk factors, we will be able to identify the high-risk group. Focus on early detection and high-quality antenatal care will help to overcome the problem of IUGR in the community.

Keywords: SGA =small for gestational age; IUGR = intrauterine growth restriction; FGR = fetal growth restriction; AGA= appropriate for gestational outcome; EFW= estimated fetal weight; AC= abdominal circumference; UA PI= umbilical artery pulsatility index; AREDV= absent or reversed end diastolic velocity; UtA =uterine artery pulsatility index; CPR= cerebroplacental ratio.

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Introduction

FGR is defined as the failure of the fetus to meet its growth potential due to a pathological factor, most commonly placental dysfunction. Clinically, this is reflected by a drop in fetal size percentiles over the course of gestation.

FGR is identified in about 3% to 9% of pregnancies in developed countries. [1] The incidence varies according to the population studied, fetal gestational age, and whether SGA fetuses were also

included. The incidence of FGR is higher in low- and middle-income regions, estimated to be 25%. [1] The prevalence of early-onset FGR is approximately 0.5% to 1%, while late-onset FGR has a prevalence of 5% to 10%. [2] Moreover, women with a prior history of growth-restricted fetuses demonstrate a recurrence rate of 20% in subsequent pregnancies. [4,3] The recurrence risk of SGA is estimated at 20%.

Table 1: Criteria to diagnose fgr

Early-onset FGR (<32 weeks)	Late-onset FGR (≥32 weeks)
EFW or AC <3rd percentile	EFW or AC <3rd percentile
or	or
UA with AREDV	≥2 of the following 3 criteria:
or	EFW or AC <10th percentile
EFW or AC <10th percentile, combined with one or more of the following:	EFW or AC crossing percentiles >2 quartiles on growth percentiles
UA PI >95th percentile	CPR <5th percentile or UA PI >95th percentile

UtA PI >95th percentile	Suboptimal uteroplacental perfusion and fetal nutrition
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Table 2: Risk factors of FGR

Maternal (preplacental) factors	Placental factors	Umbilical cord (post-placental) factors	Fetal disorders
Hypoxemia (chronic lung disease, high altitude) Anemia, Hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus, Cardiopulmonary Disease Smoking, substance abuse (cocaine, methamphetamines) Malabsorption, poor weight gain Environmental toxins: air pollution, heavy metals (lead, mercury), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA).	Maternal vascular malperfusion pathology (infarction, fibrin deposition, chronic abruption) Fetal vascular malperfusion pathology Chronic placental inflammation (e.g. villitis of unknown etiology) Confined placental mosaicism	Increased coiling Increased cord length True cord knot Single umbilical artery Marginal or velamentous cord insertion	Genetic disorders (chromosomal, micro deletions/duplications, single site mutations, epigenetic disorders) Structural anomalies (e.g. congenital heart disease, gastroschisis) Congenital infections (cytomegalovirus, toxoplasmosis, herpes, rubella, syphilis, Zika virus, malaria) Teratogen exposure (drugs, toxins)

Table 3: outcomes of FGR

Antenatal	Neonatal (short term)	Neonatal (long term)
Stillbirth Pre-eclampsia Placental abruption Preterm birth which is more pronounced in the early preterm period than at term. FGR is an important cause of iatrogenic preterm birth, as early delivery remains the main and perhaps only strategy for the prevention of stillbirth in cases of severe FGR. FGR is also an independent risk factor for spontaneous preterm birth	Neonatal mortality Neonatal morbidity (Haemorrhage, hyperbilirubinemia, hypothermia, necrotizing enterocolitis, respiratory morbidity, intraventricular haemorrhage)	Neurodevelopmental disorders Metabolic syndrome (obesity, hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular disease)

Aims and objective: To identify the risk factor for IUGR and its neonatal outcome.

Material and Method

A prospective study was conducted from January 2023 to December 2023. 300 cases were included in the study. Pregnant women having birth weight below the 10th percentile for gestational age were recruited as cases in the study.

Inclusion criteria

1. Singleton pregnancy from 28th weeks till term
2. Longitudinal lie of fetus
3. No uterine malformation in mother

Exclusion criteria

1. Multiple gestation
2. Hydraminos
3. Placenta previa
4. Fetal Malformation
5. Eclampsia
6. PROM

All cases of IUGR pregnancies who attended in Antenatal OPD were interrogated for the study. History was taken, which included age, gravida, parity, gestational age which is also confirmed by first dating scan, previous history of IUGR, last menstrual period, menstrual history and regularity of the cycle, significant past medical history (hypertension, diabetes or other comorbidity), significant family history and personal history like substance abuse, dietary patterns etc.

General examination of patients was conducted including vital charting (BP, Weight, BMI), signs of palor, icterus and pedal edema were noted. Weight of the patients was measured in each antenatal visit. Mother is expected to gain 2 kg in each 4 weeks POG. Any stationary weight gain or fall during the second trimester is suspicious of IUGR.

Abdominal examination included measurement of fundal height, abdominal girth, fetal heart rate, lie

and presentation of foetus. Symphysio-fundal height coincides with the period of gestation between 18 and 30 weeks and a lag of fundal height of 4 cm or more was considered suspicious of IUGR.

Investigations including renal function tests, 24 hours urinary protein, serum creatinine, urine routine and culture, liver function test, analysis for TORCH infection, VDRL, Glucose challenge test were carried out. Ultrasound for fetal biometry was carried out in all pregnant women with IUGR and fetal parameters like BPD, FL, AC, Amniotic Fluid Index and estimated fetal weight were obtained which were reassessed at an interval of 4 weeks. Doppler velocimetry of fetal umbilical artery was performed and S/D ratio was calculated.

Patients with IUGR were given bed rest, high protein diet, arginine supplementation, iron, calcium and folic acid supplements; dexamethasone was administered to enhance pulmonary maturity. Intra- partum monitoring was done. Depending on the obstetric profile and bishop's score mode of delivery was decided. Gestational age at delivery, APGAR score, weight, height, head circumference and Abdominal circumference of baby was noted. All neonates who required NICU care were followed up till date of their discharge.

Result

Our study comprised 300 pregnant women with suspected Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR), identified through clinical examination and/or ultrasound findings. The majority of cases (56.6%) fell within the 20-30 year age range, followed by those under 20 years (25%). Multigravida women comprised 75% (225/300) of the study population, primarily in the Gravida 2-3 group (58.3%). Rural residents accounted for 55.6% of IUGR cases. Normal BMI was observed in 63% (189) of participants, while 33.3% (100) had lower BMI. Housewives constituted 64% of the study population, followed by manual workers (17%) and sedentary workers (19%). (Table 4)

Among 300 IUGR cases, 95% (295) showed discrepancies in fundal height for gestational age, 33% (99) had severe discrepancies (>4cm), 50% (150) had moderate discrepancies (2-4 cm), 12% (36) had mild discrepancies (<2cm) respectively.

Also, among these cases, 49% (147) had normal Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI >12cm), 51% (251) had low AFI and 19% (57) had severe oligohydramnios (AFI <5cm)

With respect to doppler velocimetry results, 13 cases showed abnormal umbilical S/D ratio, indicating fetal compromise. (Table 4)

Table 4: Distribution of patients with FGR in our study

Variables	No of Pts (n=300)	Percentage (%)
Age (in yr)		
<20	75	25
20-30	170	56.6
31-35	45	15
>35	10	3.4
Gravida		
G1	75	25
G2-G3	175	58.3
G4-5	50	16.7
Rural	167	55.6
Socioeconomic status		
Upper	33	11
Middle	213	71
Lower	54	18
Occupation		
Manual worker	51	17
Housewife	192	64
Sedentary worker	57	19
BMI		
<18.5	100	33.3
18.5-25	189	63
26-30	6	2.1
>30	5	1.6
SFH		
SFH Normal	15	5
<2 cm	36	12

Cm	150	50
>4 cm	99	33
USG AFI		
<5 cm	57	19
5-8 cm	63	21
9-12 cm	33	11
>12 cm	147	49
Doppler velocimetry(S/D)		
<1	213	71
1-3	48	16
>3	39	13

The most significant maternal risk factors observed in our study were Idiopathic factors (26.3%) followed by Anemia complicating pregnancy (21.3%, n=64), Gestational hypertension (16%, n=48), including severe preeclampsia (6.7%, n=20)

and chronic hypertension (2.7%, n=8), Diabetes (12.3%, n=37) comprising Type 2 diabetes (8%, n=24) and previous history of IUGR (9.3%). (Table 5)

Table 5: Distribution of risk factors of FGR in our study

Risk factors	Cases (n=300)	Percentage
Idiopathic	79	26.3
Maternal hypertension	48	16
Anemia	64	21.3
Previous history of IUGR	28	9.3
Chronic renal disease	6	2
Drug intake	2	0.6
Diabetes mellitus	37	12.3
Hypothyroidism	18	6
Antepartum hemorrhage	18	6

Out of 300 cases, 62% delivered at term (38-40 weeks) followed by preterm (<37 weeks) in 34% cases. Only 4% delivered post-term (41-42 weeks). In majority of cases that is 46%, induction of labour was done while 13% came with spontaneous labour and in 42% elective caesarean was done respectively. Out of all these cases, 24% delivered vaginally and 66% underwent emergency or elective caesarean section. (Table 6)

Table 6: Delivery outcomes of patients with IUGR in our study

Variable	No. of patient (n=300)	Percentage
POG(weeks) at delivery		
<37 week	102	34
37-40 week	186	62
41-42 week	12	4
Mode of termination		
Spontaneous labour	36	12
Induction of labour	138	46
Elective Caesarean section	126	42
Mode of delivery		
Normal delivery	72	24
Forceps delivery	6	2
Vacuum delivery	24	8
Elective caesarean	126	42
Emergency caesarean	72	24

Neonatal outcome with respect to Apgar Scores at 5 minutes in our study predicted 12.6% (38) with scores between 4-7, requiring paediatric resuscitation with minimal support while 86.2% (258) had scores >7. Neonatal outcome with respect to birth weight suggested 62.4% (187)

weighed 2.5-3.0 kg, 25.5% (77) weighed <2.5 kg while 12.1% (36) weighed >3.0 kg respectively in our study. Therefore, the majority of neonates had favorable Apgar scores and birth weights in our study, with most requiring only minimal resuscitative measures. (Table 7)

Table 7: Neonatal outcomes in terms of apgar score at 5mins, birth weight and neonatal complications noted in our study

Variable	IUGR Neonate	Percentage
APGAR at 5 mins		
<4	4	1.2
4-7	38	12.6
>7	258	86.2
Birth weight		
<2.5 kg	77	25.5
2.5-3 kg	187	62.4
>3 kg	36	12.1
Neonatal complication		
Birth asphyxia	24	8
Neonatal jaundice	36	12
MAS	18	6
Sepsis	30	10
No complication	192	64

Out of 300 IUGR cases in our study, birth asphyxia was seen in 24 (8%) cases, requiring NICU admission while 18 (6%) cases had Meconium Aspiration Syndrome (MAS), 36 (12%) cases had neonatal jaundice and 30 (10%) cases had Neonatal sepsis during course. NICU admissions were necessary for management of these complications. Unfortunately, there were 5 (1.7%) still births or neonatal mortality cases noted in our study. (Table7)

Discussion

Fetal growth regulation is a complex process influenced by multiple factors, including environmental, maternal, placental, and intrinsic fetal conditions, which can lead to Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR). Research has consistently shown that socioeconomic status plays a significant role in IUGR development. Studies by Ashwani et al. [7], Sinha and Kurude [8], and Singh and Ambujam [9] demonstrated a strong link between low socioeconomic status and increased IUGR prevalence. Specifically, factors such as poor housing quality, limited employment opportunities, low education level, inadequate water supply, adversely impact maternal health and nutrition, contributing to IUGR. In our study, low socioeconomic status was found to be a significant factor affecting fetal growth.

In our study, the participant's parity status was evenly distributed. However, existing research by Motghare et al. [10] suggested that first-time mothers (primiparity) face a higher risk of IUGR. Women with multiple pregnancies (multiparity) are also more likely to develop IUGR, as found by Ashwani et al. [7]

Consistent with our findings, most studies identify anemia and hypertensive disorders during pregnancy as significant risk factors for fetal growth restriction. However, Ashwani et al. [8]

noted that antepartum hemorrhage is a crucial risk factor for IUGR, which was not found to be significant in our study.

The majority of studies conducted on maternal risk factors of IUGR showed that anemia and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy were significant causes of fetal growth restriction supporting the findings of the current study. However, Ashwani et al. found that antepartum hemorrhage was one of the important risk factors of IUGR which was not significant in the current study [7].

Research by Mohammad et al. [11] revealed a significant link between IUGR and a history of previous abortion. Similarly, studies like those by Shrestha et al. [12] found that mothers who had experienced IUGR in previous pregnancies were more likely to have recurrent IUGR in subsequent pregnancies. However, our study found no significant correlation between IUGR and various maternal obstetric and medical factors, including: history of abortion, previous IUGR, infections, perinatal/neonatal mortality.

Additionally, Seravalli et al. [13] reported a non-significant trend towards a higher incidence of assisted reproductive techniques in IUGR cases compared to controls.

Studies have shown that fetal growth restriction (FGR) increases the risk of cerebral palsy (4-6 times higher in newborns below 10th percentile) [13] and stillbirth (strong association) [14]. Recognizing FGR as a cause of perinatal death reduced unexplained stillbirths from 67-70% to 15% [15, 16].

Research has identified several risk factors for Low Birth Weight (LBW) and Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) babies, including maternal weight (<45kg) and height (<145cm) [17], low socioeconomic status and educational level, leading

to poor health consciousness, nutrition, and antenatal care [18], short interpregnancy interval [19]. However, our study found no significant association between IUGR and previous history of abortion/stillbirth, spacing between pregnancies, maternal weight, antenatal visits.

A separate study in India by Narang A et al [20] identified the following conditions as primary contributors to IUGR toxemia of pregnancy (30.09%), hypertensive diseases of pregnancy (5.8%), diabetes mellitus (1.94%), medical disorders (3.88%), anemia and intrauterine infection (0.97%). The most significant maternal risk factors observed in our study were Idiopathic factors (26.3%) followed by Anemia complicating pregnancy (21.3%, n=64), Gestational hypertension (16%, n=48), including severe preeclampsia (6.7%, n=20) and chronic hypertension (2.7%, n=8), Diabetes (12.3%, n=37) comprising Type 2 diabetes (8%, n=24) and previous history of IUGR (9.3%).

Conclusion

Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) remains a pervasive issue during pregnancy globally, driven by diverse factors. Research identifies two distinct IUGR phenotypes - early and late - with varying perinatal morbidity and mortality rates. Effective management requires integrated monitoring tools for early prediction of adverse outcomes, as IUGR is linked to long-term consequences including growth deficits, neurodevelopmental delays, poor academic performance, and childhood behavioural issues. To mitigate the IUGR burden, collaborative efforts between medical and social sectors are crucial in identifying high-risk pregnancies and providing comprehensive care, ultimately improving outcomes for affected individuals.

Clinical implication

Effective management of pregnancies complicated by Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) involves:

1. Regular antenatal screening.
2. Comprehensive assessment of fetal anatomy.
3. Close prenatal monitoring.
4. Initiation of anticoagulation or antiplatelet therapy in select cases.

Research suggests that the optimal window for prophylactic treatment is between 16 weeks, when placentation is complete. Therefore, current research efforts are focused on developing first-trimester diagnostic tools for IUGR, aiming to improve early detection and intervention.

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